

HARNESSING GEOTHERMAL FLUIDS FOR ENERGY AND CRITICAL METAL EXTRACTION: A CASE STUDY OF LITHIUM AND TRACE ELEMENT CO-ENRICHMENT IN A HIGH-MINERALIZED WATER SOURCE IN ARMENIA

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Abstract. Geothermal fluids represent a dual resource for sustainable energy production and critical metal extraction, offering strategic benefits for Armenia’s energy security and industrial development. This study explores the potential of geothermal waters in Armenia for lithium recovery, contributing to both renewable energy and critical metal supply chains. Building on previous research on geothermal brine metal enrichment, we analyzed over 100 water samples from selected Armenian hot springs and groundwater sources, testing for 36 elements. Results revealed a significant surface lithium concentration of 16,542 ppm in one of the groundwater samples, indicating strong potential for lithium extraction from brines. Additionally, arsenic levels exceeding 44,351 ppm suggest proximity to economically valuable mineralized zones, as arsenic is often associated with gold, silver, and copper deposits. These findings highlight the need for further geological and industrial investigations to assess extraction feasibility, enhance resource utilization, and support Armenia’s transition to a sustainable energy future.

Keywords: Geothermal energy, lithium extraction, critical metals, Armenia, sustainable energy, mineralized waters.

1 Introduction

The world is currently facing an urgent need to transition to sustainable and renewable energy sources to address the challenges posed by climate change, environmental degradation, and the depletion of fossil fuels. Geothermal energy, with its capacity to provide a continuous and low-carbon source of power, stands at the forefront of these renewable technologies. In addition to energy generation, the increasing global demand for critical raw materials such as lithium—used in battery technologies, electric vehicles, and renewable energy storage—

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has created new opportunities to integrate multiple value streams from geothermal resources. Traditionally focused solely on electricity generation or direct heating applications, geothermal power plants are now being explored for their potential in the simultaneous extraction of valuable minerals such as lithium from geothermal brine. This innovative approach enhances the economic viability of geothermal projects and aligns with global sustainability goals.

This research explores the potential of geothermal water resources in Armenia, with a particular focus on their content of critical metals, such as lithium, to evaluate their viability for extraction.

1.1 Importance of geothermal energy for Armenia's energy security

The Republic of Armenia faces specific energy security challenges due to its reliance on imported energy and limited renewable energy infrastructure. Over the 15-year period from 2009 to 2024, fossil fuel imports—including petroleum products and natural gas—have constituted approximately 70% of the country's primary energy supply. Among these, natural gas dominates with a 60% share, making Armenia particularly sensitive to external supply disruptions (figure 1) [1].

Fig. 1. Armenia's Primary Energy Supply Sources (Average 2009–2024)

While nuclear energy is also a significant contributor to the energy mix—accounting for around 18%—it is dependent on imported nuclear fuel. To address this energy vulnerability, Armenia has prioritized the expansion of renewable energy sources (RES), with geothermal energy identified as a strategic solution. Geothermal systems, unlike intermittent solar and wind, offer baseload power generation, making them a stable and sustainable cornerstone for future energy independence [2].

Several studies have been conducted in Armenia to explore the potential for electricity generation from geothermal energy, some of which have advanced to the level of techno-economic feasibility assessments and even exploratory drilling at geothermal sites. However, from the standpoint of energy production alone, these projects still require further in-depth investigation to demonstrate more compelling indicators of economic viability.

In Armenia, the rapid expansion of solar energy presents challenges related to operational regimes, planning flexibility, and the overall stability and reliability of the power system. In contrast, geothermal power plants offer distinct technical advantages, providing stable baseload generation that enhances system reliability without the need for extensive energy storage infrastructure (figure 1) [1, 3].

Table 1. Comparison of RES for Grid Stability and Energy Security in Armenia

Criteria	Geothermal	Solar	Wind
Power Supply Type	Baseload (24/7)	Intermittent (daylight-dependent)	Intermittent (wind-dependent)
Capacity Factor	70–90%	15–25%	25–40%
Grid Reliability Impact	Stabilizing	Destabilizing without storage	Destabilizing without storage
Energy Storage Requirement	Low to none	High (for grid balance)	Moderate to high
Planning & Dispatch Flexibility	High	Low	Low to moderate
Land Footprint	Low	High	Moderate
CO ₂ Emissions	Very Low	Zero	Zero
Suitability for Armenia	High (untapped local potential)	Medium (storage-dependent scalability)	Medium (site-dependent, seasonal limits)

While solar and wind energy are essential components of a diversified energy mix, geothermal energy offers unmatched stability and dispatchability, making it a critical asset for improving Armenia’s energy security—especially as the country increases its share of variable renewables.

1.2 The role of critical raw materials (CRMs) in sustainable development

CRMs are foundational to the technological, economic, and environmental aspirations of the 21st century. Lithium, cobalt, and nickel are indispensable for manufacturing high-performance batteries, which are central to both EV technology and grid-scale renewable energy storage [3]. Yet, the global supply of lithium remains highly concentrated—Australia, Chile, and China collectively account for the vast majority of global production. This geographic concentration presents geopolitical risks and supply chain vulnerabilities, especially for countries with limited domestic production capacity.

For Armenia, the exploration and potential extraction of lithium from geothermal brines—such the high-mineralized water source investigated in this research—offer a strategic opportunity. Developing local CRM resources can support clean energy development and position the country as a contributor to the global green transition.

1.3 Dual resource utilization: geothermal energy and lithium extraction

The co-production of geothermal energy and CRMs, particularly lithium, presents a promising dual-resource strategy. If subsurface temperatures exceeding 180°C can be confirmed at depths of up to 5 km for the high-mineralized water sources investigated in this research, conditions will be suitable for the deployment of high-enthalpy geothermal systems capable of generating electricity and thermal energy. Simultaneously, the presence of lithium concentrations offers the potential for extraction from the same geothermal brines [4].

1.4 Objective of the study

This research aims to explore the dual-resource potential of the geothermal system in Armenia by assessing their chemical composition, characteristics, and critical metal content, with a particular focus on lithium (Li).

The research presents a comparative assessment of lithium (Li) and arsenic (As) concentrations across different geothermal contexts, supported by a correlation analysis to identify patterns and relationships among elements for one of the investigated sources.

In addition, the study develops a preliminary model for lithium concentration at depths up to 5 km, corresponding to high-enthalpy geothermal conditions ($>180^{\circ}\text{C}$). Based on these geochemical and thermodynamic insights, the research assesses the industrial and economic potential of implementing an integrated system for geothermal energy production and lithium recovery from the identified high-mineralized water source in Armenia.

2 Background and Literature Review

Historically, much of the scientific groundwork was established during the Soviet era, and this study builds upon a careful review of Armenian-language publications and geological reports from that period, many of which remain valuable yet underutilized in modern CRM assessments. Several publications indicate the presence of metal-rich geothermal waters, particularly in regions such as Hankavan, Jermuk, Arzni, and Sisian, where naturally occurring thermal waters were partially characterized in terms of their physicochemical properties [5]. In addition to geothermal characteristics, analyses also noted the presence of economically valuable elements, particularly, the Hankavan region alone contains approximately 56 tons of boron and 14 tons of lithium, alongside rubidium, cesium, and germanium—indicating untapped potential for CRM recovery from surface and subsurface water resources [6,7].

Despite these findings, the potential for lithium reserves in Armenia's mineral and thermal waters remains largely underexplored. Lithium reserves in Armenia could be significantly higher if lithium concentrations at depths of several thousand meters were studied, where higher temperatures ($>180^{\circ}\text{C}$) increase lithium solubility. This reinforces the need to investigate deep geothermal systems as both energy and lithium sources.

In countries such as the United Kingdom and Germany, dual-use systems are being developed to simultaneously extract geothermal energy and lithium from subsurface fluids [8]. A similar model could be applied in Armenia, where geothermal and high-mineralized waters containing lithium and other rare elements exist.

3 Experimental Procedures and Data Interpretation

This section outlines the methodological framework employed in the study, encompassing the selection of geothermal and mineralized water sources, the sampling and analytical procedures, and the techniques used for data processing and interpretation. The resulting data were used to evaluate the co-enrichment of lithium and arsenic, model subsurface temperature conditions, and compare geochemical patterns with international geothermal systems.

3.1 Selection of Study Sites

Based on available quantitative data compiled from literature sources, a comprehensive sampling campaign was conducted across various geothermal and mineral water sites throughout Armenia. A total of 100 samples were collected from diverse hydrogeological environments, including drainage and waters Artesian water samples from the Ararat Valley, Yerevan Salt Lake brine sources, simplified mineralized waters discharged from tailings into nearby rivers, mineral and thermal waters from different regions of Armenia. This compilation serves as a foundational reference for identifying priority sites for further geochemical investigations, with a particular emphasis on lithium and other critical elements.

3.2 Water Sampling and Analysis

Each water sample was collected using clean, acid-washed polyethylene bottles to avoid contamination. Every bottle was carefully labeled with the exact location, time, and date of collection. Additionally, GPS coordinates were recorded for all sampling points, ensuring the precise traceability of each sample's origin. Samples were immediately filtered through 0.45 μm membrane filters to remove suspended particulates. Filtrates intended for metal analysis were acidified with ultrapure nitric acid (HNO_3 , $\text{pH} < 2$) to preserve the dissolved element composition. Samples were stored at 4°C and transported to the laboratory for further analysis. The chemical analysis was conducted according to ISO 11885:2007, which defines standardized protocols for the determination of elements by Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectrometry (ICP-OES). An Agilent 5110 ICP-OES system, known for its high matrix tolerance, dual-view capability, and advanced optical design, was used for the measurements. The instrument provides detection limits in the low ppb range and ensures repeatability and accuracy of trace element analysis. The analytical performance was routinely validated using certified reference materials, method blanks, and duplicates. The analytes included, but were not limited to Li, K, Na, Ca, Mg, As, B, Sr. The essential concentrations of lithium and other key elements are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Concentrations of Lithium and Other Elements in Groundwater Samples

Elements (ppm)	Sample Names							
	73	136	71	50	53	72	138	66
As	24,106	44,351	0,603	0,488	0,175	1,816	0,903	0,091
Ca	434,727	853,214	9,783	270,728	377,08	13,543	353,243	364,32
K	266,45	225,347	126,501	123,513	80,211	117,239	12,642	74,643
Li	17,494	16,542	6,981	6,886	4,547	2,04	1,916	1,229
Mg	77,438	97,837	115,622	112,362	75,217	47,581	200,155	273,27
Na	10339,2	11876,9	1335,64	1301,42	894,93	1197,15	1368,98	2196,8
S	156,181	259,248	65,679	63,928	35,442	75,364	56,772	191,18
Sr	25,766	32,498	0,006	3,351	2,297	0,083	3,967	5,937

3.3 Data Processing and Interpretation

As part of this study, a scatter plot was developed to visualize the relationship between lithium (Li) and arsenic (As) concentrations for the sample 136 (Table 2). To contextualize the findings, the Armenian data were compared with geothermal systems in other regions known for similar element concentrations, including Los Humeros, Mexico, Kyushu, Japan, Baden-Baden, Germany – characterized by high-temperature geothermal fluids with significant arsenic levels and moderate lithium content, in addition to geothermal energy utilization (Fig. 2).

To estimate the subsurface temperature at a depth of 5,000 meters, the geothermal gradient—which represents the rate of temperature increase with depth in the Earth's crust—was applied to the thermal water system associated with sample 71, from which data were obtained. For the calculation, a surface temperature (T_0) of 35°C was used as the baseline. A representative gradient of $35^\circ\text{C}/\text{km}$ is utilized in this analysis, reflecting the mid-range of such geothermal environments.

Fig. 2. Lithium vs. Arsenic concentrations in geothermal sources with temperature representation

$$T = T_0 + G \times d \quad (1)$$

$$T = 35^\circ\text{C} + (35^\circ\text{C}/\text{km} \times 5 \text{ km}) = 35^\circ\text{C} + 175^\circ\text{C} = 210^\circ\text{C}$$

In geothermal systems, lithium concentrations generally increase with depth, attributed to enhanced water–rock interaction over extended residence times at elevated temperatures. However, due to the lack of a universal enrichment factor, a comparative and empirical approach is adopted.

Analogous geothermal provinces, such as the Upper Rhine Valley and the Salton Sea, demonstrate enrichment factors ranging from 5x to 50x between surface and deep fluids. Given these observations, a conservative enrichment factor of 15x to 30x is applied for the sample 71: $\sim\text{Li concentration at } 5000 \text{ m} = 7 \text{ mg/L} \times (15 \text{ to } 30) = 105 \text{ to } 210 \text{ mg/L}$. Thus, the estimated temperature at a depth of 5000 meters is approximately 210°C and the projected lithium concentration in geothermal fluids is within the range of 105 to 210 mg/L.

4 Results and Discussion

Modeling results of the above mentioned fluid reserves provide a basis for calculating both energy production potential and lithium extraction capacity. With an average lithium concentration of 157.5 mg/L (mid-range), and a flow rate of 2 L/s, annual Lithium Carbonate Equivalent (LCE) Production is calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Li content per year} &= 157.5 \text{ mg/L} \times 2 \text{ L/sec} \times 3600 \text{ sec/hr} \times 24 \text{ hr/day} \times 365 \text{ days} = \\ &= 9,933,840 \text{ g/year} \approx 9.93 \text{ tonnes of Li/year} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{LCE production (conversion factor } 5.32) \approx 52.83 \text{ tonnes LCE/year}$$

Electricity Production Estimate: At 210°C , geothermal fluids are capable of supporting binary cycle power generation. Using standard conversion efficiencies (10–12% for binary plants), this could support an estimated 1–2 MWe gross electrical capacity, depending on sustained flow rates and reservoir pressure.

4.1 Comparison with similar Geothermal Power Project

The United Downs Deep Geothermal Power Project in the UK operates at a similar temperature range, with 3 MWe gross capacity and 1.59 MWe net output, while providing up to 10 MWth of thermal energy. Armenia's geothermal system, while smaller in scale, shows comparable thermal conditions, supporting the feasibility of co-generation of electricity and lithium recovery.

4.2 Extremely high arsenic concentration and potential mineralization

The analyzed geothermal fluid exhibited an arsenic concentration of 44.351 ppm (Sample 136), which is significantly elevated and suggests potential geological associations with mineralized zones, including gold, silver, and copper deposits. Such co-enrichment aligns with patterns observed in other geothermal regions, where arsenic often serves as a tracer for hydrothermal mineralization. The presence of arsenic and lithium under high-temperature conditions may indicate proximity to economic mineral deposits, warranting further exploration. Statistical evaluation shows a positive correlation between lithium, arsenic, and temperature, suggesting common geochemical processes driving their mobility. The chemical profile of the samples 136 and 73 is consistent with geothermal systems in Mexico (Los Humeros) and Japan (Kyushu), both known for arsenic-lithium co-enrichment.

4.3 Implications for Energy Security and Sustainability

If the modeled conditions—subsurface temperature of 210°C and lithium concentration of 157.5 mg/L—are confirmed through drilling and field validation, the geothermal site studied in this work could serve as a proof-of-concept for integrated geothermal energy and lithium extraction systems in Armenia.

The construction of a pilot-scale demonstration plant under these parameters would not only validate the technical and economic feasibility of such dual-resource utilization but would also create a blueprint for modular, small-scale geothermal units. These modules could then be adapted and deployed in other regions of Armenia with confirmed thermal and geochemical potential, promoting decentralized clean energy development and regional economic growth.

Furthermore, the co-location of energy generation and resource extraction aligns with global trends in sustainable and efficient resource use, strengthening Armenia's position in the regional transition to clean energy and strategic autonomy in critical materials.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

This study has demonstrated the significant potential for dual-resource utilization of geothermal fluids in Armenia, specifically for renewable energy generation and critical metal extraction. Through comprehensive geochemical analysis, modeling, and comparative assessment, it was established that geothermal fluids in the studied region exhibit high lithium concentrations (up to 157.5 mg/L, mid-range) and elevated subsurface temperatures (estimated at 210°C at 5,000 meters depth). These conditions are favorable for binary cycle electricity generation and direct lithium extraction (DLE).

The projected electrical output of approximately 161 kWe and potential production of 52.83 tonnes of lithium carbonate equivalent (LCE) per year underline the feasibility of integrated geothermal projects on a small-scale modular basis. If confirmed through drilling and pilot plant development, this model could serve as a replicable framework for similar geothermal fields across Armenia, supporting national goals in energy independence, clean technology deployment, and critical raw material security.

Future research activities will focus on targeted exploratory drilling to confirm subsurface temperatures and lithium concentrations, providing critical validation of the modeled resource potential. A pilot-scale demonstration plant is proposed to evaluate real-world performance of co-generation of electricity and lithium extraction. Beyond validation, the next steps will include detailed techno-economic modeling of full-scale deployment scenarios, advanced brine treatment and sorbent testing under local geochemical conditions, Life-cycle assessment (LCA) and environmental monitoring of integrated operations, and

comprehensive mapping and geochemical screening of other geothermal regions in Armenia to identify further high-enthalpy, lithium-rich systems.

These activities aim not only to de-risk future investment but also to position Armenia as a regional leader in sustainable geothermal resource utilization and critical raw materials supply for the clean energy transition.

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